

Preliminary data

A restrictive treatment of postural deformities (between the ages of 14 and 22) is highly effective and causes a natural development of the maxilla and mandible.

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Abstract

From 2007 to 2011, a large-scale study was conducted in India and Bangladesh by Dr. Rahul Gupta. The aim of this study was to determine whether modern methods of treating postural deformities, such as physiotherapy and muscle training, are actually superior to "old-fashioned" methods such as orthoses or plaster beds. After successfully collecting data, the study had to be discontinued for funding reasons. The study leaders at the time have now sent us all the documents in anonymized form so that we can evaluate them. Since this will be a long paper, we are publishing the most important preliminary data for the time being, since the Indian colleagues have yielded astonishing results; not only with regard to posture, but also with regard to a more natural (larger) formation of the upper and lower jaws with an overall improved facial shape.

Patients and methodology

360 essentially healthy adolescents aged 14 to 18 years with posture issues were recruited. Indication for treatment was scoliosis, mild to moderate in severity. Patients were placed in three nursing clinics, with access to their families at any time. Of these 360, only 12 discontinued participation prematurely. The length of stay in the treatment program was from the beginning of the medical interventions until the patient were 22/23 years of age, because the Indian study design assumed that physical growth in male adolescents is complete by this time.

Group 1

Sixty patients were treated with daily physical therapy and strength training to build muscle. They also received orthodontic treatment. They were educated in the sanatorium and led an age-appropriate daily life without abnormalities. 9 patients in this group discontinued treatment; from the records, poor compliance and family reasons were the causes. The average age at the beginning of treatment was 15.2 years.

Group 2

Another 60 patients were fitted with a plaster bed (Fig. 1 and 2) in which they had to lie for 23 hours per day. They left the plaster bed for half an hour for muscle building exercises under supervision and for personal hygiene. 30 of these patients received standardized orthodontic treatment, 30 did not. The average age at the start of treatment was 14.9 years, representing a length of stay in the plaster bed of 7.1 years. These patients were professionally cared for and taught by teachers to graduate from school despite treatment. Three patients in this group dropped out of treatment, with the reasons given as "family events."

Group 3

The third group á 60 patients received head, neck and upper body orthosis (Fig. 3 and 4) This group was instructed daily in muscle building exercises without removal of the orthosis. Removal took place only three times a week for basic cleaning. Also in this collective, 50% received orthodontic treatment. The average age at the beginning of treatment was 15.8 years, which meant a length of stay with orthosis of 6.2 years. This group was also educated in the sanatorium. Attention was paid to jaw growth, as this is closely related to spinal posture, according to Schreber et al.

Data

In each case, the respective treatment ended on the 23rd birthday. In addition to the general medical condition, the posture was assessed - but also the success of the orthodontic treatment and the jaw growth. The scores were given on a scale of 0 (no improvement compared to the start of treatment) and 10 (complete achievement of ideal posture). The scoring system was also applied to jaw growth.

Group 1

Posture at start of treatment:	on average 3.4 point	range (0.9-5.3)
Posture at end of treatment:	on average 5.9 points	range (4.1-6.9)
Jaw formation at start of treatment:	on average 2.2 points	range (0.6-3.4)
Jaw result with braces:	on average 5.2 points	range (4.4-7.3)
Jaw result without braces:	on average 2.4 points	range (0.8-3.6)

Group 2

Posture at start of treatment:	on average 3.1 points	range (0.7-5.1)
Posture at end of treatment:	on average 9.4 points	range (7.9-9.8)
Jaw formation at start of treatment:	on average 3.2 points	range (0.5-5.2)
Jaw formation with braces:	on average 9.1 points	range (8.2-9.6)
Jaw result without braces:	on average 8.4 points	range (6.7-9.0)

Group 3

Posture at start of treatment:	on average 2.5 points	range (0.3-4.5)
Posture at end of treatment:	on average 9.3 points	range (8.1-9.6)
Jaw formation at start of treatment:	on average 2.9 points	range (0.2-5.7)
Jaw result with braces:	on average 8.9 points	range (7.2-9.5)
Jaw result without braces:	on average 8.7 points	range (6.9-9.3)

The general condition in both physical and mental terms was comparably good to very good in all three groups at the end of the treatment. No joint stiffness, no bedsores, intact musculature and regular organ development (sonography), BMI on average 21.8 (18.9-23.6)

Preliminary Summary

The available data indicate a superiority of conservative treatment approaches, which were standard methods of orthopedics until the 1960s, but are no longer used today as too restrictive and "yesterday" in affluent countries. There is an instinctive aversion here to long-term treatments that limit freedom of movement. However, this aversion lacks a solid data basis. It is primarily an attitude and not a scientific finding. The restrictively treated patients could have stopped the treatment at any time, even without the permission of their parents. They did not.

A notable secondary finding is the consistently excellent formation of the maxillae and mandibles in the conservatively treated groups (Fig. 5). Research has shown that these data support the claims of orthotropics. This is a specialty of orthodontics that focuses on controlling growth in the facial area, contributing to overall improved muscle function as well as head movement. Orthodontic treatment based on orthotropics provides more space for teeth and tongue. This treatment method is not on correcting the position of the teeth alone, but also about head and body posture, as well as breathing. A well formed neck reduces pull effects on the jaw muscles up to >85% (Fig. 5).

Conclusions

Postural deformities continue to cause a high symptom burden in middle aged individuals and are one of the most common reasons for sick leave. Orthopedics should therefore not shy away from interventions that showed very good and sustainable results until the 1960s and now also in the study presented here. What is more, these data also indicate that orthotropics practicing orthodontists should make head-, neck-, and upper-body-orthoses or plaster beds a normal part of their appliances. Those who are practicing orthotropics can and should use these combination of orthoses and braces as a standard, not an exception. Due to the need for care for patients in plaster beds, hard-plastic fibreglas orthoses, which are worn permanently, are the best instrument - in combination with guided, muscle training while the orthosis remains fixed and is only taken off every 3 to 5 days for taking a short shower and having a skin inspection.

Outlook

The reasons and a detailed interpretation will be part of a paper to be published in the near future. We think this is necessary so that the years of effort of the Indian colleagues will not have been in vain. Moreover, it is more than questionable whether such a study would ever pass an ethics committee in the industrialized nations of the global North. Thus, by obtaining the data anonymously, we have at our disposal an insight that is unparalleled.

Conflicts of interest and ethics.

None declared. The relevant ethics committee approved the trial for team Gupta in 2007 and 2009.

Literature

Will follow in the actual study.

Acknowledgements

We thank the team led by Dr. Rahul Gupta for their perseverance, collegiality, and courage. We also thank Dr. Diamandis for using the LCG Research infrastructure to publish this paper.

Sketches provided by Dr. Rahul Gupta

Fig. 1
Plaster bed (in this case made of hard plastic)

Fig. 2
Plaster bed (upper body cast type with halo fixation)

Fig. 3
A classic halo orthosis

Fig. 4

A standard orthosis for the upper body, neck and head (metal and hard plastic)

Fig. 5

The main jaw muscles are being compromised in patients with an irregular posture. In a well treated patient the jaw is not negatively influenced by the muscles around the neck area. This "separation" is key for a normal jaw and face development.

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